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Summary: The past decades have witnessed an increasing interest in stylistics and related areas, including different pragmatic aspects and implications. Innumerable publications and many international conferences have explored the interface of language and style in actual use. Teaching literature in the classroom as part of language teaching is the area which has received most attention. Today literary texts are recognised as an important vehicle for raising language awareness and training. This applies not only to lexical and grammatical accuracy, but also to literary awareness and stylistic sensitivity. A stylistic insight helps to foster comprehension going beyond the surface meanings of words and reading between the lines of spoken and written discourse (McRae and Boardman [1984] 1989).

Key words: Contextualized stylistics, Discourse stylistics, Pedagogical stylistics, Cognitive stylistics, Applied stylistics, stylistic awareness, Stylistic literacy.

Contextualized stylistics:

Several trends in the development of stylistics have emerged over recent decades. Contextualized stylistics has a special focus on the contextual aspect, exploring the relationship between language and context, and viewing contextual elements of literature as an aid to interpretation. This approach has created many valuable studies of individual works of literature (Fowler 1966, 1975, 1981; Verdonk 1993, 2002; Verdonk and Weber 1995; Short and Verdonk 1998; Bex, Burke and Stockwell 2000).

Discourse stylistics:

Discourse stylistics focuses on use of language and the stylistic features essential for understanding and appreciation of longer stretches of text (Carter and Simpson 1989; McRae [1987] 1990; Cook 1994; McCarthy and Carter [1994] 1995; Carter 1996: 1–15; Emmott [1997] 1999 et al.)

Pedagogical stylistics:

Pedagogical stylistics has emerged to view the teaching of literature from the pedagogical standpoint (Bex 1988; Short [1988] 1992; Carter and Nash [1990] 1995; Carter and Long 1991; Widdowson 1992; Zyngier 1994, 1999, 2000; Carter 1997; Clark and Zyngier 2003 et al.)

Cognitive stylistics:

Cognitive stylistics is interested in the interaction between thought and language, figurative use of language, construction of new meanings and forms, and other cognitive aspects of language use (Lakoff and Turner 1989; Steen 1994, 2006; Semino and Culpeper 2002; Gavins and Steen 2003; Semino 2008 et al.). Steen argues for “emerging concerns with metaphor in applied linguistics” ([2007] 2009: 402). Interest in stylistics and new developments in it persists, as is shown by publications and conferences of the 21st century.

Applied stylistics:

Applied stylistics is an area which explores practical use of the principles, discoveries, and theories of language, literature, and stylistics, including cognitive stylistics. It is an umbrella term which denotes application of the stylistic competence of the language user in the fields of

teaching, curriculum design, translation and interpreting, lexicography, glossography, compilation of notes and comments on literary texts, socio-cultural studies, visual representation, advertising, and marketing. Theoretical contributions of cognitive stylistics have provided cognitive insights in practical applications, especially the study of texts (literary, non-literary) and multimodal representations, and established a new way of thinking and viewing stylistic techniques as patterns of thought in language. Applied stylistics extends our understanding of the role of stylistic use, offering a wider perspective, creating awareness of the presence and operation of stylistic features, and modifying the views and principles underlying teaching and curriculum design. Emphasis on the applied value of a stylistic approach is of great importance when developing teaching materials based on the study of both literary and non-literary texts. A stylistic approach is also essential for skills training in various applied areas and developing stylistic awareness of creative instantiations of figurative language in general and Pus in particular.

Stylistic awareness:

In stylistic use of Pus, stylistic awareness implies a number of essential aspects; first and foremost it means an awareness of:

- Significant changes in standard form and meaning;
- Figurative meaning and creation of new meaning in discourse;
- Associations, associative links, and figurative networks;
- Cohesion and stylistic cohesive ties in the text.

Acquisition of stylistic skills and competence takes a great deal of time and needs to be sustained as an ongoing process. It starts with openness to discursal use and figurative meaning with the aim of developing a feel for language use, including figurative meaning, the emergence of a new discourse form and an ability to comprehend associations and create new ones. To achieve this aim, teachers need to reflect more on the kind of materials they use and encourage learners “to develop their own thinking skills” (McRae 1996: 30) and their creative skills in particular. My main concern is to examine ways in which instantial use of Pus is relevant to language teaching and learning, translation, advertising, and other areas of applied stylistics.

Stylistic literacy:

The importance of stylistic awareness lies in development of the learner’s perception of language in use and his or her response to it. Stylistic literacy is a functional ability to use stylistic skills competently for applied purposes and activities. It is a skill that will help to apply language more purposefully and effectively. Stylistic analysis provides a deeper insight into language use and text organization. This in turn leads to more efficient teaching and learning, which provides a basis for other areas of applied stylistics. Further development of both theory of cognitive stylistics and theory of phraseology will generate more awareness, which involves abilities and skills to perceive, comprehend, and infer.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. The Oxford Handbook of Applied Linguistics (Kaplan 2002: 3–515) sees applied linguistics as a new area of research; Grabe calls it “an emerging discipline for the twenty-first century” (2002: 3–12). It is surprising that the handbook does not deal with application of the stylistic competence of the language user in any area at all, which means that applied linguistics does not include applied aspects of stylistic use in the understanding of the authors.

2. For literary awareness, see Zyngier (1994, 1999: 35). She argues for the emergence of a new discipline – Literary Awareness – and shows how it can be beneficial to L2 students (Zyngier 1994: 95).

3. The aim of socio-cultural studies is to enhance social, cultural, and linguistic understanding (Canale 1983; Bex 1988; McCarthy and Carter [1994] 1995; Carter 1996, 1997; Wierzbicka 1997; Skandera 2001; Pope 2005; Sabban 2006). Cognitive linguistics focuses on connections between language, mind, and culture (see, for instance, Kövecses, 2005, 2006; Gibbs 2008: 197–307) while phraseology explores Pus across languages and cultures (see, for instance, Granger and Meunier [2008] 2009b: 191–309; Szerszunowicz 2008).

